

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Desktop Interface for Freesound-based Sampler Audio Plugin

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Supervisor: Frederic Font

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Abstract

Began as an open-source, hardware music sampler, SOURCE is powered by the extensive collection of Freesound. It benefits from Freesound API to retrieve sounds for the user to work on their creative musical process. The first appearance of SOURCE stood as a proof of concept device that shows the interaction between the hardware device and online sound collection can be managed. On top of hardware implementation, SOURCE was designed to work on a desktop as a stand-alone or audio plugin. In this thesis, a new interface to enhance the user experience by the fundamental design rules and basics of human-computer interaction is designed. The old interface was analyzed according to visual design rules such as Gestalt Principles and semantically organized for the visual counterpart for the conceptual design. Afterward, the implementation of the new interface was realized by benefiting from third-party libraries in the defined tech stack. The outcome of this thesis and the first interface were evaluated by Creativity Support Index to measure the quality of the new interface due to its nature as a creativity support tool. The result has shown the improvement in the creative aspect of the SOURCE but the small data sample size ($N=3$) led us not to draw solid conclusions. Nevertheless, as future steps, the possible features that can be added to the SOURCE are provided in the conclusions.

Keywords: Freesound; Internet of Things(IOT); Smart Musical Instruments; Sampler Software; Digital Music Instrument

Chapter 1

Introduction

Freesound has been a well-known collaborative repository and a hub for people who would like to upload their sounds or access any sound and download them for over 17 years. Freesound website was launched on April 5, 2005, and since then the interest and participation in this repository made it reach nearly half a million sounds as of May 2021¹. Not only serves as an open-source platform for sounds, the capabilities of such a repository made it a great source for over 490 papers². Even in 2022, there are 78 papers referencing Freesound in their content; in general, Freesound has been a great source for datasets such as ARCA23K, Clotho, and more but on top of that, many types of research have been carried out to discover the potential of such a large sound collection³.

One of the particular explorations of the potential of Freesound is SOURCE, a community music sampler that is subject to this thesis. SOURCE is an open-source hardware music sampler fueled by the extensive collection of Freesound and in 2021, the paper on SOURCE got the best demo award and the industry award in Audio Mostly 2021[1]. Started as a hardware sampler by Frederic Font as a side project, and the potential of this project required a new design for its desktop interface.

¹<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Freesound>

²<https://labs.freesound.org/papers/>

³<https://labs.freesound.org/datasets/>

1.1 Motivation

SOURCE is a free sampler audio plug-in that can be used by many people. As the project started as a hardware sampler, it was also supported on the desktop as VST and stand-alone version. The motivation of this thesis comes from a goal to create a more user-friendly, easy-to-navigate, simple at first sight interface that can serve any person that has advanced knowledge in music production or not. The first interface of SOURCE, is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: SOURCE Sampler First Interface

1.2 Objectives

The design of the new interface of SOURCE was influenced by the freeness and the comfort of accessing any sound from Freesound. Working on sound with any kind of end goal welcomes all people with any level of musical knowledge. As an open-source sampler that satisfies the principle of accessibility, the design was planned to be also inclusive for people that would like to introduce themselves in music making. Therefore, the navigation in the interface was designed to be very flat-out and direct.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

In this chapter, we present the state of the art of this thesis in three main categories. Firstly, we give a review of existing samplers in the music technologies, elaborate on human-computer interaction which is one of the core fields that our study falls into, and finally, bring in design processes along with design principles and styles.

2.1 History of Samplers

Whilst several experiments had been conducted by them, making use of innovative recording mediums such as optical film, one could say the first sampling machines appeared with the emergence of the tape recorder. As it progressively replaced all recording mediums in studios and radio stations in the early 1950s, it soon began to be used in creative manners. We can mention the Phonogène, patented by Pierre Schaeffer, initiator of *Musique Concrète*, that allowed pitch shifting of a tape loop, as well as the Multi-track, patented by Hugh Le Caine in Canada in 1955, and allowed individual speed variations of up to ten tape loops simultaneously. Those early innovations led to what could be considered the first commercially successful sampling, the Mellotron, in 1963. It consisted of 35 individual 8-second tapes, triggered on key press and rewinded at key release.

As it led to multiple creative uses by a variety of artists, it was soon made obsolete by

digital sampling machines, which appeared commercially in the early 1980s with the Fairlight CMI. It provided a velocity-sensitive keyboard, a lightpen usable to draw envelopes, 32 sliders as well as decay, attack, damping, filters, and loop control to generate and manipulate waveforms. It was the first machine to enable both waveform generation and pre-recorded sample manipulation[2].

Computer-aided music then led to the development of new standards such as the Steinberg VST format and virtual instruments in general. Nemesis's GigaSampler was the first software sampler, delivered with a sound library and featuring the option to import third-party ones. In the following years, virtual instrument development advanced to provide users with more ability to produce music and design sounds. In our context, we aim to give examples of software samplers that brought novelty to the sampler domain.

2.1.1 Waves CR8 Creative Sampler

Released on the 15th of February, 2022, Waves CR8 Creative Sampler aims to enhance the creativity of users with a touch of easiness. It can be integrated by the Cosmos sampler finder¹ which is an AI-powered standalone sample management software that extracts audio features like BPM, key, and length. All the samples in the local can be organized by these features so that the user can focus on the creation rather than manually evaluating and categorizing the sounds. On top of this novel feature, 5 stretching algorithms, timbre shaping by built-in filters and ADSR envelopes, and 4 LFO/sequencer modulators are provided in this sampler.

2.1.2 Initial Audio Slice

Primarily focused on the creation of loops and beats, Slice enables users to work on rich loops and beats by using existing sample packs or recorded samples by the user. Samples can be manipulated by using built-in features such as fade-in, fade-out, stretching, and pitch shifting. On the waveform section, the user can slice the

¹<https://www.waves.com/plugins/cosmos-sample-finder>

²<https://www.waves.com/plugins/cr8-creative-sampler>

Figure 2: Waves CR8 Creative Sampler ²

audio and work on sliced sections which open a new way of creativity. This creative process is backed by three sequencers: slice, drum, and bass.

Figure 3: Initial Audio Slice ³

2.1.3 Glitchmachines Polygon 2.0

Polygon⁴ is a hybrid synth sampler that is perfectly suitable for sound design in specific. The huge amount of controls provided by this sampler is taken a step

³<https://initialaudio.com/product/slice-loop-slicer-plugin/>

⁴<https://glitchmachines.com/products/polygon/>

further by the granular mode. The granular engine offers many granular synthesis settings with a modern dual oscillator. All these features are wrapped in a very simple interface that may lead a user to achieve maximum tool transparency during the creation.

Figure 4: Glitchmachines Polygon 2.0

2.2 Human-Computer Interaction

Human-computer interaction(HCI), is a multidisciplinary study field that focuses on the design of computer technology and its interaction with users. The reason behind being a multidisciplinary topic is that HCI is an intersection of disciplines such as psychology, cognitive science, ergonomics, sociology, engineering, business, graphic design, technical writing, and most importantly computer science and system design/software engineering.[3]

2.3 Design in HCI

Design, which is a crucial process that defines the experience of a user and the quality and usability of interfaces, functions as a noun and a verb at the same time[4]. In the context of the appearance of a product, design is a noun but if the concern is establishing a system that complies to reach a goal, the word becomes a verb. If a

design is defined as a great one, a user must be able to accomplish many objectives such as enhancing creativity, introducing new ways of thinking, and enabling a hard daily task to be completed shortly and easily. Therefore, where design is used as a verb, a set of rules must be defined to enhance the process of design.

2.3.1 Interactive Design Loop

A design process is an approach that helps designers to figure out steps to be taken to find a solution to an existing problem. This process primarily focuses on breaking down the whole project into smaller and manageable chunks. One of the approaches to determine the design process is the Interacting Design Loop (IDL from now on) which was developed by R. Kimbell as shown in Figure 5. IDL uses the following steps to obtain an effective design.

- **Gathering and analyzing information:** The main focus is learning what is unknown. To accomplish this, all the assumptions are questioned, intensive and extensive research is carried out and new ideas are generated.
- **Determining performance criteria for a successful solution:** At this stage, what is known is specified and rules are set.
- **Generating alternative solutions and building prototypes:** Rather than a single solution, multiple solutions are generated and a great number of analysis methods are used.
- **Implementing choices:** The content, scope, and intent of the process are formalized. The very first possibilities are represented and realized as prototypes.
- **Evaluating outcomes:** The possible prototypes are assessed, tested, evaluated, and judged.
- **Production:** A synthesis of the first arising solutions, a prototype, and its specifications are released for making multiples to a manufacturer.

Figure 5: Interacting Design Loop

2.3.2 Information Design Process

Just applying and following the fundamentals of a design process may not be sufficient, some requirements define the quality of a design product. According to S. Watzman and M. Re[4], the design should motivate users, increase ease of use and accessibility, increase the accuracy and the retention of the information and focus on the needs of its users. This set of requirements is also known as Information Design Process (IDP from now on).

IDP consists of two phases: the audit and the design development. The audit is a process where the aim is to create a blueprint for the project. In this process, a set of questions are answered but this process is not only limited to the beginning of the project design but continually asked. These questions are:

Audit A

- *Who* are the product users?
- *How* will this product be used?
- *When* will this product be used?
- *Why* will this product be used?
- *Where* will this product be used?
- *How* will the process evolve to support this product as it evolves?

Audit B

- What is the most efficient, effective way for a user to accomplish a set of tasks and move on to the next set of tasks?
- How can the information required for product ease of use be presented most efficiently and effectively?
- How can the design of this product be done to support ease of use and transition from task to task as a seamless, transparent, and even pleasurable experience?
- What are the technical and organizational limits and constraints?

In the audit part, these questions are asked to clarify the target users and define their needs while using the product. This phase is very crucial due to the ability to define the limitations, and requirements and establish a solid structure for the product. In the second part of IDP, which is called design development, the audit results are used as a guideline. The design development phase is an ongoing process to meet the needs of the project. Since its iterative, a deadline for this process should be defined to not fall into an infinite loop of iteration. By setting a deadline, the iteration time of the process is limited and in the defined period, design and testing are realized. At the end of this phase, finally, a prototype is implemented and monitoring is tested, approved, and specified[4]. The lifecycle of IDP is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Information Design Process

[4]

Depending on the conditions, time limitations, and requirements, any of the design processes can be selected to carry out a design project. A design project might be centered around one expression medium such as music or visuals, in the context of this thesis, our interface is a subject to visual design.

Visual design is a process of using color, shapes, and typography to clarify the visual information, provide good communication with the user, and allows the user to grasp the interface easily. A great visual design allows users to accomplish the task via an interface, enables them to access the content without frustration, and enjoy the tool to the fullest. On top of these criteria, the visual design was also found to have an impact on the emotions of the user[5]. When a user interacts with a well-design product, the experience results in a positive emotional state that also affects the judgment towards the product itself. Combined with aesthetic pleasure, a design concerned with all these aspects encourages the user to interact with the product and results in a good user experience. To accomplish a good visual design, there are a set of basic elements and principles that can be applied in the visual design process as explained below.

2.4 Basic Elements of Visual Design

As clay is the basic element of a sculpturer, line, shape, negative space, volume, value, color and texture are the fundamental elements for a visual design. These elements constitute the basics of a visual design and the creativity of a unique visual piece is based on them. A brief explanation of these elements follows.

Line

Line, at its simplest definition, is connecting two dots and defining a length and width along with a direction. The line serves as a foundation for shapes and textures.

Shape

The shape is the feature a person notices when they look at an object from a long distance. It is a self-contained entity and differs from a line by having two dimensions

without mass or depth[6].

Negative Space

Negative space can be defined as the space around the positive shape. This element is important to visually highlight an element in the design surface.

Volume

As shape exists in two dimensions, the volume brings the third dimension to the visual design. On top of the length and width of the shape, the volume adds an extra layer which is depth.

Value

Visual perception is highly dependent on light in the visible spectrum and value focuses on light and dark. Value is important to reveal the shape or form of an object in visual design.

Color

Color is an aspect of any object that may be described in terms of hue, lightness, and saturation. Objects appear as colored to a human eye because of the way it interacts with light⁵

Texture

The texture is a feature of objects that is defined as the quality of the surface.

2.5 Principles of Visual Design

The elements mentioned in the previous section alone are not sufficient only for themselves but bring value while used within a set of principles. The principles of visual design define how to use these basic elements to solve a specific problem. As we mentioned earlier, defining the problem and creating a roadmap can be placed

⁵<https://www.britannica.com/science/color>

within the design process but this process on its own in the context of visual design is not adequate. Therefore, utilizing these principles is crucial and in the context of this thesis, only relevant principles will be briefly explained.

2.5.1 Gestalt Principles

Perceptual organization refers to the process of structuring the disintegrated bits of visual information into larger units that a person can experience as environmental objects. The Gestalt psychologists, who studied perceptual organization for the very first time[7], suggested that organization consists of grouping and segregation processes. This suggestion was followed by several general principles[8] in the 1920s and reached today as an impactful set of principles in the domain of visual design. In the context of this thesis, we will only elaborate on the principles that align with the goal of the new interface design.

Law of Continuation

This law of Gestalt dictates that elements arranged in order as a line or curve are perceived to be related compared to elements that are not present in a line or curve, see Figure 7. The Law of continuation relies upon the order of elements and symmetry and also can be defined as the human eye's instinctive action to follow a direction derived from the visual field [9].

Figure 7: Law of Continuity ⁶

Law of Closure

According to K. Smith-Gratto and M.M. Fisher[10], closure is an explanation where an individual completes a visual that is incomplete to avoid the distraction created

⁶<https://www.usertesting.com/resources/topics/gestalt-principles>

by this incompleteness. An object, for example, a circle as shown in Figure 8, tends to be perceived as a full circle whereas the object itself misses a piece of it.

Figure 8: Law of Closure ⁷

Law of Proximity

The proximity principle states that elements close to each other are perceived as a group. For this purpose, it is important to locate elements belonging to a pre-defined group close to each other, as shown in Figure 9; applying this principle creates a clear cue for the user to understand.

Figure 9: Law of Proximity ⁸

Law of Similarity

This law states that on a surface, the elements sharing similar characteristics e.g. shape, color, and motion are tend to be perceived as a group by the human eye. Also, perceiving these elements as a unified group creates a sense of similarity in function. According to Kubovy et al[11], conjoint similarity and proximity enhance the performance of the effect linearly.

⁷<https://isle.hanover.edu/Ch05Object>

⁸<https://sites.psu.edu/psych256fa14/2014/09/14/gestalt-laws-of-perceptual-organization/>

⁹<https://vansedesign.com/web-design/gestalt-principles-of-perception/>

Figure 10: Law of Similarity ⁹

Law of Common Regions

The common regions principle is referred to as the grouping that occurs when the elements are located within a closed region. Regardless of their characteristics such as shape, and color, the closed area serves as a dominating factor for grouping. This law, from a hierarchical perspective, is more dominant compared to the law of similarity and proximity.

Figure 11: Law of Common Region ¹⁰

2.5.2 Focal Point and Hierarchy

Hashimoto et al[6] defines the focal point as the main attraction point of a design. This concept is crucial to take the attention of the user and absorb them to continue examining the design. This approach can be applied while the design needs a single point attraction but in the case of multiple focal points, these require a level of hierarchy. Visual hierarchy, if established clearly, gives the designer ability to tell the viewer what to look at first and how their eye will travel from one point to the next, which can be defined as navigation[12]. In the case of lacking visual hierarchy,

¹⁰<https://vansedesign.com/web-design/gestalt-principles-of-perception/>

the user lacks guidance on how to navigate the visual design which may result in frustration.

2.5.3 Balance

Balance can be defined as the equal harmony and distribution of visual design elements such as colors and texture. There are four types of balances identified by Evans et al[13]: symmetrical, asymmetrical, radial, and crystallographic. Crystallographic balance is the even distribution of elements, whereas radical balance is concerned with the conveyed energy and the sense of movement[[14],[15]].

2.6 An Overview of User Interface Design Styles

Since the first usable graphical user interface(GUI) was developed by researchers at the Xerox Palo Alto Research Center in 1977[16], there has been an accelerating improvement in the user interface design due to the advancement in computer abilities and user needs. In this section, we will concentrate on the latest user interface design styles that have been dominating the field.

2.6.1 Soft UI

Soft UI is a design that embraces characteristics of this style and can be defined as the color selection of pastel and vivid tones, round user interface elements, and the use of gradients along with subtle colorful shadows. Since positive emotions such as calmness can be evoked by using pastel colormaps[17] or curved shapes[18], this design style is considered to be fresh and relaxing.

2.6.2 Flat UI

In contrast to soft UI, this style embraces sharp-edged, flat elements, subtle shadows, and low hue colors; hence the interface is associated with a more professional and serious look. As a complementary to a professional look, the typography employed in this style is usually simple and classic.

2.6.3 Skeuomorphism

Skeuomorphism is a design style that focuses on mimicking the real-world counterparts of objects in visual design. This style was used in UI way before flat design and derives its essence from metaphors and affordances, therefore designs applying Skeuomorphism are intended to help users understand how to use a new interface by allowing them to apply their prior knowledge about the real-world objects it contains.[?]An example of skeuomorphic design is shown in Figure12.

Figure 12: Keyboard UI with skeuomorphic design ¹¹

2.6.4 Neumorphism

Neumorphism is considered as the hybrid of flat design and skeuomorphism and takes advantage of these styles in a way to create a minimalistic look and still maintain a resemblance with the real-world counterparts¹². Elements of the interface are dependent on the blend of light and shadow which results in the geometry of the object. Although the fresh yet resembling feeling evoked in the user by this style, accessibility is considered to be one of its drawbacks of it. The blend of colors with low contrast prevents people with low vision ability to achieve a good user experience. An example of neumorphic design is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: ROLI Seaboard Block ¹³

¹¹<https://dribbble.com/shots/14753768-Skeuomorphic-Keyboard-Figma>

¹²<https://webflow.com/blog/neumorphism>

¹³<https://www.gear4music.es/es/Teclados-y-Pianos/ROLI-Seaboard-Block/200H>

Chapter 3

Conceptual Design and Implementation

In this chapter, we present the conceptual design and the implementation of the new interface, which can be named as production process[6], based on the state of the art of this thesis explained in the previous chapter. Firstly, we explain the conceptual design which puts IDP and visual design principles into use and gives details of the technical implementation of the prototype that was designed.

3.1 Conceptual Design

The conceptual design of this thesis was carried out by using the information design process[4]. As the first step, audit A and B were completed to understand the user needs and depart from these requirements. The answers to audit A and B are shown in Table 1 and Table 2.

Once the initial blueprint for the interface design was obtained, we moved forward to the development stage. In this stage, all the information gathered in the state of the art was put into use. The steps taken in this process are as follows.

Table 1: Audit A

Audit A Questions	Answers
Who are the product users?	Music producers Sound designers Beginners in music
How will this product be used?	Standalone DAW Plugin
When will this product be used?	When user decides to work on sound
Why will this product be used?	In music production Music education No live performance
Where will this product be used?	macOS Windows Linux
How will the process evolve to support this product as it evolves?	-

Table 2: Audit B

Audit B Questions	Answers
What is the most efficient, effective way for a user to accomplish a set of tasks and move on to the next set of tasks?	Proper grouping of features
How can the information required for product ease of use be presented most efficiently and effectively?	All-in-one-page interface
How can the design of this product be done to support ease of use and transition from task to task as a seamless, transparent, and even pleasurable experience?	Quick response from interface Single container with switch control
What are the technical and organizational limits and constraints?	Only frontend languages

Analyzing SOURCE

The desktop version of the SOURCE consists of a sampler engine, written in JUCE, and plugin UI, which is an HTML file, see Figure 14.

All the features provided by the sampler engine are displayed in the first interface of the SOURCE1 in a disorganized manner that collides with the law of proximity and common regions. As the first step of the analysis, this list of features is categorized according to their relevance as shown in Table 3

Figure 14: SOURCE block diagram

1

Table 3: SOURCE parameter categorization

Main Category	Parameters
Filter ADSR	attack, decay, sustain, release, cutoff, cutoff amount, ressonance
Amplitude ADSR	attack, decay, sustain, release, pan, gain
Reverb	room, damping, wet, dry
Modulation	gain, cutoff, pitch
Velocity	cutoff, gain
Query Parameters	number of sounds, minimum and maximum sound length, note layout type

The defined categories in Table 3 served as a sub-group and in the second step, the irrelevance of these subgroups was analyzed. Filter ADSR and Amplitude ADSR were found to share common parameters and decided to be placed in the same region. Also, sound effect parameters, reverb, modulation, and velocity decided to be grouped in the same region to apply the law of common regions. In the second part of the analysis, we noticed that the focal point, which in the case of SOURCE was querying sounds to be able to continue the creative process, was not highlighted. Therefore, we aimed to create a visual hierarchy to obtain clear navigation and invisible guideline to utilize SOURCE. Finally, we categorized the functions of the input controls and assigned a knob or slider design to each of them to apply the law of similarity and finalized the design by applying symmetrical balance.

Design Style Selection

In the context of this thesis, four different design styles are researched. One of the targets stated in Audit A, people with entry-level in music production, directed the design style selection towards skeuomorphism since in many cases flat designs lack visual clues that could help communicate easily their function but skeuomorphism fulfills this requirement [18]. Also, to provide other target audiences with a unique user experience, we aimed to select a more minimalistic and elegant design. Therefore, the hybrid version of flat design and skeuomorphism, neumorphism decided to be the design style of the new interface.

Additional Features

SOURCE provides four different launch modes as loop, loop feedback, gate, and trigger. In the first interface, the start and end points of loop modes are handled via sliders. This choice of adding control of start and end points results in space occupation in the interface. Therefore, these control parameters are decided to be transformed into a region selection option on the displayed waveform to fulfill ease of use criteria in IDP. Also, as stated in Audit A, one of the target audiences was defined as people with entry-level in music production. To enhance the engagement and learning process of this target audience, implementing a 2D ADSR envelope was decided. On top of these new features, a built-in keyboard decided to be integrated into the new design. As distinct from virtual keyboards, this built-in keyboard is designed to combine trigger and gate modes with loop modes. Finally, for user experience, two-color modes light and dark decided to be implemented.

3.2 Implementation

The technical implementation of the design is done in a Dell Inspiron 13 7000 laptop, operating on Ubuntu 20.04.2 LTS, using Visual Studio 2022 as IDE. The layout of the interface is implemented by using CSS grid layout and CSS Flexible Box Layout². The layout is divided into seven sub-containers: query, waveform, sound

²<https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/CSS>

list, 2D ADSR Envelope, ADSR control parameters, sound effects, and keyboard. For 2D ADSR Envelope, a third-party library is used³. Since the waveform display implementation of the first interface did not support region selection for loop mode, a JavaScript library Wavesurfer⁴ to visualize waveforms is used. The sliders as control components are replaced with JQuery Knob⁵ to match with the initial design sketches. For event handling such as triggering a key from the keyboard, jQuery⁶ library is used. Finally, for the neumorphism affect, a out-of-box CSS code generator⁷ is utilized. The result of the implementation which is the prototype of this thesis is shown in Figure 15 and 16.

Figure 15: SOURCE Dark Mode

³<https://github.com/mohayonao/adsr-envelope>

⁴<https://wavesurfer-js.org/>

⁵<https://github.com/aterrien/jQuery-Knob>

⁶<https://jquery.com/>

⁷<https://neumorphism.io/>

Figure 16: SOURCE Light Mode

Chapter 4

Evaluation Methodology

In the previous chapters, the principles and rules to employ during the design of the new interface and the approach to implementing this interface were explained. In this chapter, we will elaborate on the evaluation strategy of the old and new interfaces will be explained.

Creativity is not a phenomenon that can be easily defined or evaluated but when the process of creativity includes the usage of a tool, also known as creativity support tools(CST from now on), there are approaches to evaluate the effectiveness of the tool. The current evaluation techniques are not fully suitable when it comes to CSTs. For example, in the context of human-computer interaction, time and error metrics are utilized for the evaluation of the tool. These metrics can lead the researcher to be mistaken due to a couple of scenarios if applied in CSTs. For instance, a user might be spending a long time during the creative activity due to engagement but not because of the complexity to succeed in the goal. Another HCI metric is determined as productivity but a product that is a result of a creative process implies uniqueness and comparison to another work does not give a meaningful result.

Since employing evaluation techniques from other domains might fail due to the unique essence of CSTs, there are special methodologies for measuring them. These methodologies include qualitative methods like observation, think-aloud studies, and interviewing and are sometimes paired with quantitative methods. As in many meth-

ods, these methods are considered to have drawbacks such as expensiveness and time consumption.[19] Due to these drawbacks and the ability to retrieve information on how to improve some aspects of the tool provided by chosen evaluation methodology, in this study, an evaluation methodology named as Creativity Support Index(CSI for now on) is used.

4.1 Creativity Support Index

Developed by E. Cherry et al, CSI is similar to the NASA Task Load Index Survey but is designed specifically for evaluation creativity support tools. During the design of CSI, the departing point was chosen the theory of creativity. Since there are many theories about creativity, E. Cherry et al come up with a set of concepts such as engagement, expectation, and collaboration deriving from various theories by researchers e.g. Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi, Rubin et al and Read et al. After evaluation of BETA CSI, E. Cherry et al concluded in setting factors of CSI as exploration, collaboration, engagement, effort/reward tradeoff, tool transparency and expressiveness[20].

This evaluation method is applied in two parts the first interface and the new interface. The participants are asked to create a thirty-second track with the old and new interface. After they were satisfied and they defined their track as complete, they were asked to complete the CSI survey. In the first part, a survey of statements corresponding to the aforementioned factors is presented with Likert scales from 1 to 20 as shown in Appendix A and Appendix B. In the second part of the survey, each factor is compared against the other five to assess the relative importance of these factors to the participant of the particular activity under study as shown in Appendix A. For the new interface, on top of CSI questions in the first part, two more questions were added to analyze the mode selection of users and to get feedback to finalize the prototype as a research product which differs from the prototype in many ways as explained in the next section.

4.2 Digital Music Instruments as Research Products

In the field of HCI and Digital Music Instruments(DMI from now on), prototypes carry an important role, and evaluation of these prototypes can give a detailed insight into the idea brought into reality. Nonetheless, the improvement of the prototype can be an endless loop, unlike a research product. According to Odom et al[21], a research product should be designed to provoke users in their environment, their design must be complete and they must be able to fit into an everyday scenario. In the domain of DMI, the design and evaluation phases are iterative and therefore, they are hard to be treated as a finished artefact[22]. As Jack et al[22] stated, an instrument cannot be considered as finished in terms of material completeness but could be considered as both an attitude towards an instrument being functionally complete within a performance context.

Departing from this approach, the feedback gathered from participants is used to iterate over the prototype and our prototype is finalized as a research product.

Chapter 5

Results

In this chapter, CSI results of the experiments with 3 participants are presented.

5.0.1 CSI Evaluation

In the evaluation part, the compiled version of the first and the second interface was shared via email along with the instructions. They were asked to launch the plugin in their choice of digital audio workstation, compose 30 seconds of the track and record it, and finally answer the corresponding questionnaire. 2 of the participants used macOS version 12.6 and macOS 5.3.2. stated that the compiled version of both did not load in their choice so they were discarded from the experiments and this issue was noted as a bug to be solved and examined. 3 participants completed the experiment without any issues and their questionnaire responses were received automatically.

The CSI scores are calculated by multiplying each factor ranking from the first part of the survey by the count for that factor in the second part of the survey and summing them together. The sum is then divided by 3 to arrive at an index out of 100[20]. The final results are noted in Table 4.

Table 4: CSI Scores of first and second interface

Participant	First Interface CSI (%)	Second Interface CSI (%)
1	76.6	84.0
2	3.33	71.3
3	47.0	70.0
STD	30.095	6.3115
MEAN	42.309	75.1

5.0.2 Research Product Stage

The questionnaire of the second survey included optional two extra questions to gather feedback from the subjects to figure out the extra requirements from the users' side to evaluate the performance of the tool in the production phase thoroughly. First question, the mode selection was selected dark by all users. The reason for this selection specified by subjects as:

- Light mode lacks highlighting elements
- Dark mode is more eye-friendly

Two subjects answered the question on feedback and these answers were used to improve the prototype and finalize it as a research product. These feedbacks are as follows.

- Gain knob is keeping its value and can't be reduced after modification
- When more than 10 sounds are queried, only 1 sound return
- Query returns different results every time, which makes it difficult to go back to a previous desired sound
- Fade-in and fade-out features would be a plus
- Possibility to zoom in the waveform for more fine grain settings of the loop

In the context of this thesis, feedback such as including fade-in and fade-out was discarded due to the implementation in the sampler engine domain. Apart from

features that require implementation or improvement on the sampler engine, we focused on enhancing the interface. Therefore, zooming in and out of the waveform is implemented by utilizing Wavesurfer features. Also, the bug appearing while querying 10 or more sounds was found to be an issue with not displaying the query message. In some cases, the query returns no sound and this is not reflected on the interface. Departing from these feedbacks, the improvements are made and the code can be accessed from repository¹.

¹<https://github.com/ffont/source>

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Further Work

6.1 Conclusions

In this thesis, we aimed to design a new interface by applying fundamental visual design principles in a well-defined design process. The designed and implemented interface and the first interface were evaluated by using the CSI method. The results have shown that the new interface had a higher CSI score on average but this result can be extended by selecting user groups according to their expertise. In the second part, gathered feedback led us to improve the new interface so users can engage and utilize SOURCE with fewer issues and more enthusiasm. Alone itself, this feedback depends on the possibilities of the SOURCE and its new interface, therefore, the future of the SOURCE is more dependent on the novel approaches to take it a step further. Possible ideas are explained in the next section.

6.2 Further Work

F. Font[1] presented four future directions of SOURCE as the continuation of the research. In this thesis, developing a new interface to interact with SOURCE as in its hardware version is realized. One of the future directions stated is to investigate the notion of acoustic similarity to browse and select sounds in a 2D space similarity. The main limitation of this investigation was found to be the display area size in

the hardware implementation. This idea brings the possibility of implementing a similar discovery technique as in Freesound Explorer, explained in section 6.2.1.

6.2.1 Freesound Explorer

F. Font et al[23] presented a web application that stands as a visual interface for exploring Freesound content in a 2D space. Freesound Explorer uses Freesound API to retrieve sounds that were given by user queries and creates a 2D space by the similarities of the sounds by utilizing CataRT system developed by Schwarz et al[24]. This web application uses the space of a browser page and unfortunately, this requirement was not satisfied in the hardware version of SOURCE.

In our interface implementation, we considered the possibility of implementing a feature similar to Freesound Explorer and designed the sound list area in a way that corresponds to the space requirement as shown in Figure 17. Compared to the original web application of Freesound Explorer, the size of the region might be still inadequate but with the help of scrolling, this feature can be realized and the design can be preserved.

Figure 17: SOURCE New Interface sound list area

6.2.2 Interactive ADSR

In the new interface of SOURCE, a 2D envelope graph is implemented. This envelope can be controlled with corresponding knobs only, but this control mechanism can be advanced by a user interaction responsive envelope. For instance, the learning

platform of Ableton¹, shown in Figure 18 provides an interactive linear envelope graph for the beginner level users. This interaction can enhance the engagement of the user which is one of the CSI factors and may result in a better score.

Figure 18: Ableton Learning Synth platform ADSR envelope

¹<https://learningsynths.ableton.com/en/envelopes/putting-the-envelope-together>

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Appendix A

New Interface CSI Questionnaire

Holahola!

Welcome the the questionnaire of the second interface of SOURCE.

LET'S GO! >

Question 1

*As you may have noticed, there are two modes of SOURCE: Dark and Light. Which one would you prefer to use in your musical activities with SOURCE?

Dark Light

Question 2

If you would like to, please explain your reason for selecting dark/light mode.

Please enter your response

NEXT >

SKIP

Question 3

***It was easy for me to explore many different options, ideas, designs or outcomes without a lot of tedious, repetitive interaction.**

0: Agree, 20: Disagree

NEXT >

Question 4

***I was able to work together with others easily while doing this activity.**

0: Agree, 20: Disagree

NEXT >

Question 5

***I was very absorbed/engaged in this activity -I enjoyed it and would do it again.**

0: Agree, 20: Disagree

NEXT >

Question 6

***What I was able to produce was worth the effort required to produce it.**

0: Agree, 20: Disagree

NEXT >

Question 7

***While I was doing the activity, the interface "disappeared" and I was able to concentrate on the activity.**

0: Agree, 20: Disagree

NEXT >

Question 8

*I was able to be very expressive and creative while doing the activity.

0: Agree, 20: Disagree

NEXT >

Question 9

Please select which factor is more important to you from one of the two options. For instance, if exploration plays a more important role in the activity compared to collaboration, select 1.

*

Exploration: The possibility to explore your ideas, obtain a fruitful outcome without being frustrated by the interface itself.

Collaboration: The possibility to collaborate with other people while using the interface.

Effort/Reward Trade Off: Whether the effort user makes to have a final outcome is balanced with the end result.

Tool Transparency: Ability to sustain activity without thinking of the control part of the interface.

Expressiveness: The possibility of being creative and realizing the ideas while interacting with the interface.

	1	2
Exploration or Collaboration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Exploration or Engagement	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Exploration or Effort/Reward Tradeoff	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Exploration or Tool Transparency	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Exploration or Expressiveness	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Collaboration or Engagement	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Collaboration or Effort/Reward Tradeoff	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

NEXT >

Question 10

Thanks for answering all the questions!

Since this is not a final product, I would like to hear any improvement you think can be made with this interface or any bug you encountered.

Please enter your response

SUBMIT ✓

Press ENTER key to submit

Never submit passwords in [Browser abuse](#)

Appendix B

First Interface CSI Questionnaire

Hi.Hello.Hola.Hey!

Welcome the the questionnaire of the first interface of SOURCE.

LET'S GO! >

Question 1

*It was easy for me to explore many different options, ideas, designs or outcomes without a lot of tedious, repetitive interaction.

0: Agree, 20: Disagree

NEXT >

Question 2

***I was able to work together with others easily while doing this activity.**

0: Agree, 20: Disagree

NEXT >

Question 3

***I was very absorbed/engaged in this activity -I enjoyed it and would do it again.**

0: Agree, 20: Disagree

NEXT >

Question 4

***What I was able to produce was worth the effort required to produce it.**

0: Agree, 20: Disagree

NEXT >

Question 5

***While I was doing the activity, the interface "disappeared" and I was able to concentrate on the activity.**

0: Agree, 20: Disagree

NEXT >

Question 6

***I was able to be very expressive and creative while doing the activity.**

0: Agree, 20: Disagree

NEXT >

Question 7

Please select which factor is more important to you from one of the two options.
For instance, if exploration plays a more important role in the activity compared to collaboration, select 1.

*

Exploration: The possibility to explore your ideas, obtain a fruitful outcome without being frustrated by the interface itself.

Collaboration: The possibility to collaborate with other people while using the interface.

Effort/Reward Trade Off: Whether the effort user makes to have a final outcome is balanced with the end result.

Tool Transparency: Ability to sustain activity without thinking of the control part of the interface.

Expressiveness: The possibility of being creative and realizing the ideas while interacting with the interface.

	1	2
Exploration or Collaboration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Exploration or Engagement	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Exploration or Effort/Reward Tradeoff	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Exploration or Tool Transparency	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Exploration or Expressiveness	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Collaboration or Engagement	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Collaboration or Effort/Reward Tradeoff	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

NEXT >